

COGNITIVE DEVELOPMENT OF COMMUNICATION AND OTHER ACTIVITIES OF A TEENAGER

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Abstract. *In the article, the leading activity in adolescence is reading, communication and labor activity, immaturity and inexperience of a teenage child force him to seek support from those around him, adolescents put friendship, comradeship and mutual assistance above all else, under the influence of their peers, a teenager can satisfy his needs and desires. Cognitive theory places a special emphasis on the influence of intellectual processes on human behavior.*

Keywords: *system of constructions, determinated, external universe, imaginary Cognitivists, subjective, interest, progress.*

ПОЗНАВАТЕЛЬНОЕ РАЗВИТИЕ ОБЩЕНИЯ И ДРУГОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ ПОДРОСТКА.

Аннотация. *В статье ведущей деятельностью в подростковом возрасте является чтение, коммуникативная и трудовая деятельность, незрелость и неопытность ребенка-подростка вынуждают его искать поддержки у окружающих, подростки превыше всего ставят дружбу, товарищество и взаимовыручку, ставят под влиянием сверстников подросток может удовлетворить свои потребности и желания. Когнитивная теория уделяет особое внимание влиянию интеллектуальных процессов на поведение человека.*

Ключевые слова: *система построений, детерминированность, внешний мир, мнимые когнитивисты, субъективизм, интерес, прогресс.*

In adolescence, the leading activity is reading, communication and labor.

The primary function of adolescent communication is the identification and acquisition of elementary norms in friendship, sharing. The main feature of adolescent communication is that it is subject to the fiber friendly code. It is of great importance for adolescents to interact with their peers. Adolescents put friendship, companionship and mutual assistance above all else: such a relationship, which can continue even in adolescence. In doing so, adolescents and early-age adolescent learners are affected by niig behavior several times more strongly than their friends parents and educators. This can be explained by the fact that the immaturity and inexperience of a teenage child makes him seek encouragement from those around him. A small child needs a friend who understands his desires and helps him fulfill them. Friends of O'mir. A teenager has a special

interest in the environment of relations with equal children in a state of principled equality. This corresponds to the ethical content of the sense of personal seniority that occurs in a hoi teenager. Being in communication with adults cannot replace communication with peers.

For a teenager, the dialogue with peers breaks down into the atmosphere of his own personal relationship, in which he acts independently. He thinks that I have the right to this, defends his rights, and that is why the inappropriate, rude interference of adults in the relationship with his comrades leads to resentment and dissatisfaction of the teenager. The desire for peer interaction and collaborative activities is evident in the environment. The desire to live a team life, to have close comrades, a friend is a strong desire, as if accepted, recognized, respected by friends. It becomes an important requirement of a teenager.

The most unpleasant situation for a teenager is the dissatisfaction of the team and comrades, the unwillingness to communicate, and the most severe punishment is the interruption of open or non — friendly communication, not talking. Important norms of the code of friendship of adolescents are honor, equality, loyalty, help to a friend, honesty. Mastering the standards of friendship is an important achievement of a child in adolescence. If he cannot find such a friend among his relatives and educators, then he will surely find a person who supports his interests and aspirations, and who can satisfy the shortcomings in him with something, among foreign adults or his peers. Based on an egalitarian relationship with their peers, the teenager goes through a separate School of social relations. It is very valuable for them that they realize and understand mutual interests, the world around them, each other.

Homework for adolescents is more peer-to-peer than commitment to household chores.

Own secrets the child no longer trusts his parents, but his peer. In the process of communication and attitude with his peers, he is able to fully show his personality with freedom.

He perceives personal freedom as the right to grow up. Experienced teachers, who are well aware that it is of great importance for the teenager to interact with their peers, pay great attention to the formation of a positive social opinion among some small and small groups of students even in the classroom, trying to influence adolescents through their close friends. Some students (especially those students who stay in the duck in their studies and who are "difficult to educate") do not allow themselves to "fall" from the system of interpersonal relationships in the classroom community. Under the influence of their partners, a teenager can satisfy his needs and desires. If the satisfaction of this is a great satisfaction to him, in such cases, in relation to some of his actions or deeds. Cognitive theory of personality also has significant differences, although it is close to the views of representatives of the humanistic school. The founder of cognitive theory is the American psychologist Dj.Kelly (1905-1967) is mentioned. In his opinion, a person wants to know

only one thing - what happened and could happen in life. The main source of personality development, according to Kelly, is the social environment. Cognitive theory places a special emphasis on the influence of intellectual processes on human behavior. In this theory, each person is compared to a scientist who examines his hypotheses about the nature of objects, which gives him the opportunity to anticipate future phenomena.

Any phenomenon has the potential to be interpreted multiple times. A key concept in this direction is the concept of construct (Eng. construction-build). This concept covers the features of certain cognitive processes (perception, memory, thinking, speech). Thanks to constructs, a person not only understands the universe, but also inter-personal relationships. Constructs lying on the basis of this relationship are known as Person constructions (Francella F., Bannister D., 1987). A construct is a specific classifier mold that defines the way a person perceives himself and others.

According to Kelly's point of view, each of us hypothesizes and lives by checking it, in a word, the person we see with the help of specific constructs (classifier) is not intelligent or intelligent, 79 is capable or incompetent, etc., is concerned with solving the problem of determining. Each construct has a "dichotomy "(two poles);" intelligent/not intelligent", "capable/incompetent", etc. A person optionally chooses a dichotomic construct pole that more accurately represents the probable end that an event describes, i.e., uses a construct that allows prediction. While some constructions are suitable for giving descriptions of narrow-range phenomena, others have a wide scope of application. For example, - smart/stupid konstruk construct weather. Friendship between people, love, etc. normal relationships such as, can occur when people's constructs are monand. Imagine what can happen when two people want to enter into a successful relationship —if the moral/immoral konstruk construct is superior, and if the other does not have such a construct itself. The system on constructs is not a static (fixed) derivative, it is constantly changing under the influence of life experience, that is, the individual is formed and progressive throughout his life. In the person —ongl is superior. Unconsciousness concerns remote (subordinate) constructs. These constructions are rarely used by a person in interpreting the perceived phenomena of the universe. Kelly believes that individual freedom is limited. The system of constructions formed during 80 in human life becomes restrictions.

However, he did not consider human life to be entirely determinized (defined). In any situation, a person is imko to create alternative predictions.

According to cognitivists, the fate of a person is in his own hands. The inner world of a person is subjective, and his inner world is a derivative of his imagination, and a person interprets the outer world through the reality of his inner world. The main element of this concept is the construction of the individual. It, in turn, has two levels: 1) the structural block — the main

structures close to 50, located above the structural system. A person uses these constructions a lot with the aim of entering into interaction with other people, that is, standing in the center of consciousness. 2) peripheral constructs block — all other constructs. Since these constructs are individual derivatives, there can be from several hundreds to several thousand. Personality characteristics are manifested as the result of the joint work of these two block structures. Two categories of individuals are distinguished: a cognitively complex personality (a person with many constructs) and a cognitively simple personality (a person with a small number of constructs). A cognitively complex person is distinguished from cognitively simple individuals by the following qualities:

- 1) his mental health is much more honest;
- 2) effectively relieves stress;
- 3) his assessment of himself is high enough;

4) quickly adapts to new situations. Experimental studies have shown: over time after the adoption of a weighty decision, the subjective favorability of the positive aspects of the rejected decision decreases with increasing positive aspects of the chosen decision. A person in this way gets rid of cognitive dissonance: he assures himself that the decision he made was much better than the one that was denied. It can be concluded that difficult decisions increase the likelihood of displaying behavior in accordance with the chosen decision. Hence, according to cognitive theory, a person is a specially organized system of constructions of a person's personal experience, which is processed (perceived and interpreted). From the point of view of this approach, the individual structure of the individual

REFERENCES

1. Vohidov M., Maktabgacha tarbiya psixologiyasi, T., 1970;
2. Davletshin M., Krbiliyat va uning diagnostikasi, T., 1979;
3. G'oziyev E., Psixologiya fani XXI ayerd, T., 2002;
4. G'oziyev E., Psixologiya, T., 2003;
5. Qodirov B., Layoqat psixologiyasi, T., 1989;
6. Shoumarov G'., Oila psixologiyasi, T., 2000;
7. Karimova V., Ijtimoiy psixologiya, T., 1994.
8. Назирова, Феруза Абдуазизовна. "ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИЕ И КОММУНИКАТИВНЫЕ СПОСОБНОСТИ В РАБОТЕ УЧИТЕЛЯ." Science and innovation 3.Special Issue 18 (2024): 918-923.

9. Назирова, Фेरүза. "Kasbiy kompetentlik sifatlari." Современные тенденции инновационного развития науки и образования в глобальном мире 1.3 (2022): 363-367.
10. Yormatova, Sh, F. Nazirova, and M. Muhammadjonova. "PEDAGOGIK FAOLIYATNI TEXNOLOGIYALASHTIRISH-IJTIMOIIY ZARURIYAT SIFATIDA." Scientific progress 1.6 (2021): 1198-1201
11. Xamidovna, Mamayusupova Iroda. "EVACUATION OF THE LEVEL OF CONFLICTS IN CONFLICT SITUATIONS BETWEEN ADOLESCENTS." Confrencea 1.1 (2023): 23-27. <https://confrencea.org/index.php/confrenceas/article/view/372/375>
12. Khamidovna, Mamayusupova Iroda. "MASTERY OF MANAGING PEDAGOGICAL COMMUNICATION STUDY, GENERALIZATION AND DISSEMINATION OF ADVANCED PEDAGOGICAL EXPERIENCE." Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal 10.12 (2022): 1217-1222. <https://internationaljournals.co.in/index.php/giirj/article/view/4627/4322>
13. Khamidovna M. I. CAUSES OF FAMILY CONFLICTS //Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal. – 2022. – T. 10. – №. 12. – C. 870-872. <https://internationaljournals.co.in/index.php/giirj/article/view/3156/2907>
14. Khamidovna, M. I. (2022). The influence of older people on the formation of the spiritual environment in Uzbek families. INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429, 11(10), 360-364. https://api.scienceweb.uz/storage/publication_files/3062/8164/641d74df6fdbcb98bcbf0b0d184b0d0ba0d182be0d18074a0b0d0b2d188b0d0bd0b6be0bd29b0b8d180d29b0b8d0bb0b30b0bd.pdf